

ORACULAR REASONING AND THE LIMITS OF JUSTIFIED BELIEF IN GETTIER-LIKE ARGUMENTS ABOUT KNOWLEDGE.

ALEJANDRO MATUS
alejandromatusunfe020@gmail.com

Summary. Through a logical analysis, we show how Gettier cases, presented as counter-examples to the conception of knowledge as a justified true belief, are not consistent; they are a variation of oracular reasoning, logical fallacy in which specific type propositions, which contain a logical constant, are tangled with propositions formed by logical variables; uniqueness is confused with mere existence, the necessary and sufficient conditions with necessary but not sufficient conditions; and there are cognitive biases, for example, the neglect of base rates in argumentation.

KEYWORDS: FALLACIES_EPISTEMOLOGY_GETTIER_BIASES_TVERSKY_BELIEF_JUSTIFICATION_NECESSARY-SUFFICIENT_DEDUCTION-EXPERIENCE_LOGIC_QUANTIFIERS_BASE-RATES.

Against the conception of knowledge as a justified true belief, Edmund L. Gettier has proposed two cases as counter-examples. This has had a strong impact among the community of scholars of Knowledge Theory, where the stipulation of counter-examples of such a kind has been multiplied.

There is a widespread notion that they are logically valid reasoning, which make it necessary to correct the aforementioned categorization of the knowledge, either by modifying or by extending the conditions for describing it (cf. Dretske 1971; Goldman 1976; Nozick 1981, pp.178-180; Lycan 2006).

In this paper we perform an analysis to show that these counter-examples have logical flaws that prevent them from being valid. Failures that basically consist of a form of reasoning very similar to that of many oracles and astrological predictions, where interpreted propositions containing logical constants are mixed up with propositions composed of uninterpreted logical variables; logical quantifiers of uniqueness with mere quantifiers of existence; necessary and sufficient conditions with necessary but not sufficient conditions; and the base frequency rates (cf. Tversky-Kahneman 1982) also are confused.

To show such structural similarity, we first look at what oracular reasoning consists of, its erroneous logical structure. We then apply our results to the two cases exposed by Gettier, which depend on logical deductions. And how these consequences also apply to cases subsequently generated by another authors, concerning to empirical knowledge. So, we regard for the ways that justifying a belief can be exhausted (logical deduction or direct or indirect experience). Finally, we formulate with generality the deep and fallacious structure of the procedure.

1. Oracular reasoning.

Herodotus writes: Some Lydians

were charged by Croesus (his king) to inquire to the oracles, "Shall Croesus send an army against the Persians?". ... The judgment given to Croesus was that if he should send an army against the Persians he would destroy a great empire. ... (Croesus) was greatly pleased with the oracles ... fully persuaded that he would destroy the kingdom of Cyrus ... And so led his army to the Persian territory.

Croesus was defeated.

As the oracle foretold, brought his own great empire to an end.

Cyrus allowed him to send other emissaries

To ask if the god (Apollo) were not ashamed that he had persuaded Croesus to attack the Persians, telling him that he would destroy Cyrus' power; ... The priestess (it is said) thus replied: ... Croesus doth not right to complain concerning it. For Loxias declared to him that if he should lead an army against the Persians he would destroy a great empire. Therefore it behoved him, if he would take right counsel, to send and ask whether the god spoke of Croesus' or of Cyrus' empire. But he understood not that which was spoken, nor made further inquiry: wherefore now let him blame himself (Herodotus. Book I, 53-54, 75, 86, 90-91).

In the end, Croesus accepted this replica.

2. The logical structure of oracular reasoning.

This prophecy is a clear example of a large number of oracular and astrological predictions, with a logical structure of the following type:

- a) The prophet issues an ambiguous proposition, that is, a proposition so general that it admits more than one option as an interpretation.
- b) Someone, usually the recipient of the prediction, specifies such a proposition, giving it a unique meaning, habitually corresponding to his personal background, biases and hopes.
- c) If such a particular option occurs in the facts, the oracle claims to have succeeded. If it does not occur, the oracle evades its responsibility by blaming an erroneous specification to the interested subject. The soothsayer states that what he meant was the particular option that actually happened, which, of course, is consistent with the generality of the prediction.

We can analyze this in formal logical terms:

- a) The Augur emits a propositional function, with a variable x that can take more than one value; and not an interpreted, specific statement that gives to x a constant value. The fortune teller handles his propositional function without specifying what is equal x to. He only claims Fx .
- b) It is the interested part who gives a value to x , usually without realizing that such a role has been left to her, assuming that such an interpretative specification is implicit in the issuance of the prophet. Thus, the interested party believes that it has been provided not Fx , but, for example, Fa , with $x=a$.
- c) If Fa occurs, the oracle is considered correct ($Fx \equiv Fa$), both by the one who asks and by the soothsayer. If $x \neq a$ occurs, the augur attributes the error to the questioner; and if, moreover, $x=b$, and therefore Fb , he claims that is what he meant ($Fx \equiv Fb$) and therefore got it right. Often whoever asks ends up accepting that answer.

The structure of the fallacy is to emit a propositional function, but to consider it (unduly from a logical point of view) in itself as a more specific interpreted formula than it actually is. To take advantage that the function has more than one concretization option, but to treat it as if it were a single option in itself. To allow to be given a definite value and not be objected such value, until the specific fact that makes it true or false occurs.

If true, the propositional function is validated.

In case of falsehood, falsehood is allowed to falls under the first formula already taken as a particular option. But an implicit use is made of a second specific option, which

corresponds to the fact actually occurred. And it is believed, or affirmed, that in issuing the propositional function what was meant was the new determination.

At the beginning, the propositional function and its first specified formula are considered to have the same validity. Subsequently, are taken as identicals the same propositional function and a second formula, specified differently to the first, and contradictory to it.

3. Gettier's argument. First case.

Next, we'll apply what we have said to Gettier's reasoning. He famously wonders "Is knowledge justified true belief?" (Gettier, 1963), in addressing a conception of various epistemologists (cf. Plato, *Meno* 97a-98b and *Theaetetus* 200d-210c; Ayer, 1956, p. 34; Chisholm, 1957, p. 16), according to which the necessary and sufficient conditions for someone to know a given proposition are:

- 1) Proposition P is true;
- 2) S believes that P; and
- 3) S is justified in believing that P.

Gettier argues that such a conception is false, being able to give a counter-example. So, he sets out the following:

Suppose that Smith and Jones have applied for a certain job. And suppose that Smith has strong evidence for the following conjunctive proposition:
d. Jones is the man who will get the job, and Jones has ten coins in his pocket. ... Proposition (d) entails:

e. The man who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket.

Let us suppose that Smith sees the entailment from (d) to (e), and accepts (e) on the grounds of (d), for which he has strong evidence. In this case, Smith is clearly justified in believing that (e) is true. ... But imagine, further, that unknown to Smith, he himself, not Jones, will get the job. And, also, unknown to Smith, he himself has ten coins in his pocket. Proposition (e) is then true, though proposition (d), from which Smith inferred (e), is false. In our example, then, all of the following are true: (i) (e) is true, (ii) Smith believes that (e) is true, and (iii) Smith is justified in believing that (e) is true. But it is equally clear that Smith does not *know* that (e) is true; for (e) is true in virtue of the number of coins in Smith's pocket, while Smith does not know how many coins are in Smith's pocket, and bases his belief in (e) on a count of the coins in Jones's pocket, whom he falsely believes to be the man who will get the job (Gettier, 1963).

Let's look at this counter-example proposal:

The proposition (d) corresponds to an expression of type

$$\exists x: x=j \wedge T_x \wedge M_x.$$

Where j =Jones; T = Will get the job; M = Got ten coins in his pocket.

Here x has adopted the value of an individual constant, which always has the value of j . It refers to a specific individual who meets the conditions stipulated in the description. Although (e) is derived from (d), Gettier's argument set aside that (e) is a non-specific propositional function. Only when a specified constant has been chosen, with $x=a$, or $x=b$, or $x=s$, or $x=j$, and so on, as in (d), does it become a particularized, interpreted, formula, to which a value of truth or falsehood can be assigned regarding to a single particular object, to a single option.

Thus, Gettier in (e) takes x as if it were a yet indeterminate variable, which can take values other than j . And he derives from it a new value of x , when the case occurs that

"Smith" is the specific value that makes true to (e). He implicitly generates a new particular proposition (f). And by doing that, he is actually performing a new operation, in which $(e) \rightarrow (f)$, by replacing the variable x with the new constant $s \neq j$. Here (f) is:

f) The man, Smith, who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket.
Giving to x , "The man," the value of "Smith."

Instead of the expression derived from the original:

e) The man, Jones, who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket.
Giving to the variable x , "The man", the value of "Jones".

In other words, this is a confusion in logical quantifiers, the difference between "There is one and only one" (which predicates the existence and uniqueness of an object, and can only be, for example, $x=j$, which assigns to x a constant specific value), and "There is" (which predicates only existence, and can be $x=a \vee x=b \vee x=j$, and so on).

More accurately, it is possible to formulate (d) in a syntactically valid way as

d') $E!x:x=j \wedge Tj \wedge Mj$.
Where $E!$ =There is one and only one.

As this description includes, in a formal logical way, the assertion that the individual possesses in an exclusive manner the characteristics attributed to him, and they are not possessed by any other individual, in addition to existence it is predicated uniqueness: that there is only one object such that meets those characteristics (cf. Russell 1905).

Hence we have, equivalently:

d') $\exists x \forall y (Hx \wedge Tx \wedge Mx \wedge (Ty \wedge My \rightarrow y=x) \wedge x=j)$

That is, there is an x such that x is a man (H), that he will get the job, and that man has ten cents in his pocket; and if any man gets the job, and that man has ten cents in his pocket, that man is Jones.

The bound part $\forall y (Ty \wedge My \rightarrow y=x)$ excludes that any individual other than Jones complies with the necessary and sufficient conditions expressed by proposition P.

(d') is what John believes he knows. That if there is a man named "y" (for example, "the black-haired man" or "the man in the brown shirt" or "the green-eyed man" or "the man with ten coins in his pocket"), and that man gets the job, that man is Jones ($Ty \rightarrow y=x$).

In his argument, when he entails (e), Gettier, validly, set aside the necessary condition ($Ty \wedge My \rightarrow x=y$). But in (e) Gettier uses "The man" as a variable that can be replaced by any of a set of alternative constants, by multiple options, when in fact in (d) a single option occurs, one and only one defined logical constant.

In other words, Gettier replaces the particular with the generalization. A specific proposition, Fj , about Jones becomes a proposition, Fx , about a possible individual who may or may not be Jones; but that emanates from the assumption that he is Jones.

But then to this Fx , fallaciously, as in oracular reasoning, and inadvertently, he makes it a new and different proposition Fs , now about another constant: Smith.

What Gettier does is to give a new specific value to the variable x from the propositional function (e), that of $x=s$, distractingly generating a new proposition (f) other than (d) or (e), contradictory with (d), in an unjustified step.

And this option (f), but not the one Smith thinks he knows, (e), is the specific formula option, the proposition, which Gettier finally adopts, which is true or false when the job is assigned, or not, only to Smith, to s ; while the more general option (e) can be true by assigning the job to Smith or to Jones, or to anyone else with ten coins in their pocket. That is, to both Smith and no Smith, s and $\neg s$; Jones, or not Jones, j and $\neg j$.

The sense of (e) in Smith's belief always presupposes Jones. "The man who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket" always means "Jones" to Smith, and therefore modally

never can be replaced by "Smith" or some other name. The matter is not about the mere proposition, but about John's belief on the proposition.

It is false that Smith justifiably believes (e) without the prior univocity. What Gettier does is a fallacious change of constant regarding (d), forming so (f); and *confuses (e) with (f)*. Therefore, his Smith is not logically justified in believing that P is true under any specification option.

In Croesus's case, with either option that may happen, the priests will be able to say that the Pythia was right. What happened is that she issued a type (e) sentence, with a non-specific, ambiguous propositional function structure, with more than one option, without assigning it a value set to x. And it was then, implicitly, inadvertently, that fallaciously Croesus himself replaced the x with the constant of his liking or bias ("Persia"); and after the events, the oracle replaced it with the constant "Lydia"; just as Gettier substitutes in (d) the x with "Jones" and then in (f) replaces the x from (e) with "Smith".

4. Necessary and sufficient conditions.

The condition "One and only one" emphasizes the need to formulate the necessary and sufficient conditions to specify this "one". In addition to the general necessary and sufficient conditions for knowledge to exist, in the specific case set out by Gettier, to speak of Smith's knowledge it is necessary and sufficient that the particular conditions of existence and uniqueness be met:

- 1) Jones is the person who will get the job,
- 2) There is one and only one person who will get the job; and
- 3) Jones has ten coins in his pocket.

From the logical point of view of Smith's concrete knowledge, those three are the necessary and sufficient conditions determined by (d) for him to know that P. When he infers (e) from (d), he deletes one of those conditions, the main one, that of $E!x:x=j$; for that reason (e) no longer expresses the sufficient conditions in this specific case for Smith to believe that (d).

When of the three conditions Gettier pick ups only two in (e), and excludes that of $x=Jones$, he can only validly, not oracularly, infer that Smith knows that those two conditions are necessary, but that they are not sufficient to specify who will get the job. Nevertheless Gettier incorrectly arguments as if for Smith those two reasons were sufficient.

Assuming that (1), (2) and (3) are necessary and sufficient reasons to assert that Smith believes P, Gettier falsely assumes that (2) and (3) are necessary and sufficient reasons to assert that Smith believes proposition P. When the only valid thing is to conclude that (2) and (3) are necessary reasons, but not sufficient (when is omitted (1) with $x=j$) to claim that Smith believes P. And so one of the necessary conditions to say that Smith believes P has not been met. If we want say truly that Smith believes P, it is necessary that $\exists x:Tx \wedge Mx$, but it is not enough. It is also necessary that $x=j$.

So, Gettier, from

Smith believes that $P \leftrightarrow (1), (2) \text{ and } (3)$
(i.e., P if and only if $E!x:x=j \wedge Tx \wedge Mx$),

implicitly jumps to

Smith believes that $P \leftrightarrow (2) \text{ and } (3)$
(viz., P if and only if $\exists x: Tx \wedge Mx$).

Wrongly, he preserves the "if and only if".

When the syntactically justified is only

Smith believes $P \rightarrow (2) \text{ and } (3)$
(i.e. P entails $\exists x:Tx \wedge Mx$).

Viz., with the simple implication, but no longer with the if and only if.

Consequently, if Smith deliberates in a logically coherent way, he cannot believe that (e) is true if he presupposes those necessary reasons as sufficient. Or, if he believes that (e) is true with such assumption, then he is not logically justified to believe such a thing. As he is justified to believe that (e) is true if he presupposes those reasons just as necessary, but not sufficient.

In short, Gettier emits (e), which has the structure of a propositional function, based on (d) —with (d) as an interpreted formula. However, the option expressed by (d) does not occur, but the one expressed by a different specified formula (f). Below ground, Gettier re-specifies (e), now based on the fact actually happening according to his formulation (the expressed by the interpreted formula (f)).

And he unduly attributes the belief in the truth of this new specification to sentence (e), the propositional function from which it comes, and not only, as logically corresponds, to the new interpreted formula (f).

It's as if G, a cooking enthusiast, wants to apply the recipe for a dessert from a renowned Chef who specifies:

d) Add cinnamon (cf. "The empire of Cyrus is going to fall"; or "Jones is the man who will get the job and have ten coins in his pocket").

But G has no cinnamon at his disposal at the time, and he deduces that as (d) entails the generalization:

e) Add a spice (cf. "A great empire is going to fall"; or "The man who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket"),

then he can

f) Add pepper (with the understanding that it is also a spice) (cf. "The empire of Croesus is going to fall"; or "The man (Smith) who will get the job has ten coins in his pocket").

And in doing so, the dessert tastes bad. And so he concludes that the recipe is actually bad ... and not his way of understanding logic.

5. Gettier's second case.

Gettier says:

Let us suppose that Smith has strong evidence for the following proposition:

f. Jones owns a Ford. ...

Smith has another friend, Brown, of whose whereabouts he is totally ignorant.

Smith selects three place names quite at random and constructs the following three propositions:

g. Either Jones owns a Ford, or Brown is in Boston.

h. Either Jones owns a Ford, or Brown is in Barcelona.

i. Either Jones owns a Ford, or Brown is in Brest-Litovsk.

... Imagine that Smith ... proceeds to accept (g), (h), and (i) on the basis of (f).

... Smith is therefore completely justified in believing each of these three propositions ... But imagine now that two further conditions hold. First Jones does not own a Ford, but is at present driving a rented car. And secondly, by the sheerest coincidence, and entirely unknown to Smith, the place mentioned in proposition (h) happens really to be the place where Brown is. If these two conditions hold, then Smith does not know that (h) is true, even though (i) (h) is true, (ii) Smith does believe that (h) is true, and (iii) Smith is justified in believing that (h) is true (Gettier 1963).

In this case, Gettier only chooses three specific propositions for his disjunctions. Smith builds from (f) three statements with the structure (f) \vee X (with X a variable proposition), among them (h), where he replaces X with B: "Brown is in Barcelona".

But countless other sentences can also be formed, replacing X with other propositions, such as

h*): Either Jones owns a Ford or Brown is NOT in Barcelona.

Where $X = \neg B$; that is, (f) $\vee \neg B$ is generated. And it can be justifiably believed that all these propositions are true, being (f) true. Then, with the occurrence of B or $\neg B$, even if (f) is false, the propositional formula (f) \vee X will always be true (for B or $\neg B$ logically exhausts the universe of possible options), thanks to any of those occurrences that turns out to be true with respect to the variable X. So, while Smith justifiably believes that

h) Either Jones owns a Ford or Brown is in Barcelona,

at the same time justifiably believes that

h*) Either Jones owns a Ford or Brown is NOT in Barcelona.

So whether Brown is in Barcelona or Brown is not in Barcelona, any of those two facts that exclude each other (that are contradictory to each other), will make (f) \vee X true when happen.

What's more, the generality of the authors seems not to have realized that Gettier could have better chosen the "Is not in Barcelona" option, and his argument would not need to claim "By the sheerest coincidence", and would have much greater chance of succeeding randomly. Albeit with the same lack of logical validity.

To go from (f) to (f) \vee X is to make a valid tautological generalization, where in X any proposition fits. But any proposition which specifies X and actually be true (turning it into a constant proposition that becomes a new true sentence of the form (f) \vee X), is chosen by Gettier as the oracle does, as if it were the predicted fact, to convert (f) \vee X in a justified true belief.

Either Smith does not believe that B (or that $\neg B$) occurs actually, or he does, but in this case he has an unjustified belief, when judging that if can happen any one fact that he conceives, this gives him a concrete knowledge of something. As a result, we would enter a logical system where anything can be deduced, where any belief can be justified, an inconsistent system.

Smith has the general idea that necessarily one of those propositions is true, and the others false. But not which one is which. And by specifying Gettier one of them post hoc, according to what has happened in his plot about the reality, he is developing, in the oracular way, a new more specific proposition (h), which was not originally either in proposition (f) nor in its entailed (f) \vee X (from this, is derived (h), as well as (h*)), or an infinite number of other potential specifications that can make it be true).

Gettier omits in this case making explicit an intermediate action, that of its generalization towards (f) \vee X, from which infers (g), (h) and (i). So we have that Smith believes that (f) \vee X is true, justifiably, but also

(ii') Smith really does NOT believe that (h) is true because Brown is in Barcelona;

or, if he does,

(iii') Smith is NOT justified in believing that (h) is true because Brown is in Barcelona.

Since in both cases he could also believe justifiably and at the same time that (h*) is also true because Brown is not in Barcelona.

From the initial assumption, Smith not only believes in the disjunction; he also believes that the condition that makes disjunction true is only the part (f). Regardless of

whether part B is true or false. The oracle justifies: we said that either thing was going to happen and it happened. The oracle is not univocal, but it takes the disjunction, still unspecified, as if it were an univocal proposition, as if it were one and only one of its interpretations (adopted a posteriori), the (h).

6. Other Gettier cases.

It is expressed that

In Gettier's cases, the justified true belief is inferred from a justified false belief. ... However, ... there are examples of Gettier cases that need involve no inference (Ichikawa, 2018).

And:

What distinguishes these cases from the preceding counterexamples to sufficiency is that, in them, there are no identifiable false tacit assumptions (Lycan 2006, p. 157).

Examples of such cases may include the following:

The hindu Dharmottara asked:

Imagine that we are seeking water on a hot day. We suddenly see water, or so we think. In fact, we are not seeing water but a mirage, but when we reach the spot, we are lucky and find water right there under a rock. Can we say that we had genuine knowledge of water? The answer seems to be negative, for we were just lucky (quoted by Dreyfus 1997, p. 292).

On the other hand, the philosopher Peter of Mantua sets out:

Let it be assumed that Plato is next to you and you know him to be running, but you mistakenly believe that he is Socrates, so that you firmly believe that Socrates is running. However, let it be so that Socrates is in fact running in Rome; however, you do not know this (quoted by Boh 1985, p. 95)

Chisholm presents the following case:

A person takes there to be a sheep in the field and does so under conditions which are such that, when under those conditions a person takes there to be a sheep in the field, then it is evident for that person that there is a sheep in the field. The person, however, has mistaken a dog for a sheep and so what he sees is not a sheep at all. Nevertheless it happens that there is a sheep in another part of the field. Hence, the proposition that there is a sheep in the field will be one that is both true and evident and it will also be one that the person accepts. But the situation does not warrant our saying that the person knows that there is a sheep in the field (Chisholm, 1977, p. 93).

In all these cases, what is believed, the proposition (1) that is formulated, refers to a precise location, and to a precise object being considered (a mirage, Plato or the dog); and our possible knowledge refers only to that location and to that object. In which case, by the very formulation, we are confirmed that we had a non-true belief.

One is arguing in an oracular way, if one is to make effective the idea that a justified belief was obtained with a new proposition (2), by first generalizing the proposition (1) towards (2) (towards the ambiguous, which allows to encompass, in addition to the precise, specific, location (1), also the x points of the surroundings, or even faraway places, such as Rome).

And next, (2) is specified towards another new interpreted proposition (3) \neq (1) that is true, by incorporating a posteriori the location or the specific object \neg (1) where the favorable event appears. Even if it is different from the exact location or from the object that corresponds to (1), to which the reference was made. And so we make this generalization (2) true. Which, actually, also would become false if we replace its variable with the logical constant of specification (1), the only one that expresses in each of the cases quoted the belief that each of the postulated individuals has. Thus, (1) is false, (3) is true; and (2) is ambiguous, and there is no reason for confuse it with (1) nor with (3).

7. Limits on the justification of a belief.

Similar to the cases cited, Goldman sets out the following situation:

Henry is driving in the countryside with his son ... "That's a cow," says Henry, "That's a tractor," "That's a silo," "That's a barn," etc. ... Each object is fully in view, Henry has excellent eyesight, and he has enough time to look at them reasonably carefully, since there is little traffic to distract him. ... Suppose we are told that, unknown to Henry, the district he has just entered is full of papier-mâché facsimiles of barns. These facsimiles look from the road exactly like barns, but are really just façades ... The object he sees is a genuine barn. But if the object on that site were a facsimile, Henry would mistake it for a barn. Given this new information, we would be strongly inclined to withdraw the claim that Henry knows the object is a barn. ... It is accidental that Henry is right about its being a barn. So we withdraw our knowledge attribution (Goldman, pp. 772-773).

There is another change of constant here. Henry refers to the one and only one barn *g*, and addresses his belief to it. Nevertheless, Goldman makes a change towards the variable *x* (all the facades of the place), and then specify each of these as the constants *h*, *i*, *j*, etc., and each one is a mere façade. But he excepts precisely the one that is the case for Henry's belief, which is *g*.

There are two ways in which a belief can be justified: either by experience, or by being a logical truth.

The two cases that Gettier exposes attempt to be justified beliefs through logical truths.

In the other cases mentioned here, it is only possible to justify the belief based on experience. Therein lies why they "Need involve no inference".

There are two kinds of experience, direct and indirect. The cases of the mirage, Plato, the fake sheep and Henry can be verified (justified or denied) directly. Is enough get to where the mirage was supposed to be, turn to see the other runner clearly, get close enough to the fake sheep, or inspect the barn more thoroughly.

But they can also be justified as indicated by the facts described by the authors of these cases (except in the circumstance of the mirage, for with regard to mirages in the desert the subject might believe that they are frequent, and then it is necessary to see for believe): indirectly, by induction, noticing it or not such researchers, without turning to see clearly, without getting close enough, or without looking more carefully.

This can only happen based on previous experiences, when, for example, Socrates is known to be the person who often tends to run nearby; or is known that cases of dogs that can be confused with sheeps are much less common in the real world than that of true sheeps; or that the same goes for fakes and real barns.

From Goldman's approach, Henry does not believe that his belief is justified as a logical truth. Or if he believes it, then his belief is not justified. So Henry can only validly believe that his belief is justified by experience. But Henry does not exhaust the means available for direct empirical testing, by not doing, e.g., a more meticulous examination. Thus, Henry does not believe that his belief is justified as a sufficient direct verification; or, if he believes this, then his belief is not justified.

All that remains to Henry is the indirect experience. And if he gets to ask about the justification of his belief, it is only justifiably valid for him to recognize that it is based

on induction from his previous experience, in the absence of further profound research in direct verification.

This one, that we can call a relative deficit of direct corroboration, is the one that is replaced using induction, consciously or subconsciously.

Goldman only chooses the points that fit his argument, those of the field Henry travels through, regardless of the entire universe of barns that he may previously know, directly or by reference, where what abundantly deprives are the real barns and not the facades that simulate them.

What is accidental, in the very first place, is that Henry is passing through one of the few places in his country and the world where facsimiles predominate. And considering that his judgment presupposes what he knows about the vast majority of barn facades, that they correspond to real constructions, then he succeeded not by chance, but because, in fact, that was the most likely by induction from his prior knowledge.

The latter is the only thing that can give a footing to the author to think that Henry's belief is justified. And allow us not to require, in order to consider it so, that it should have done a direct empirical check, a more thorough, readily available, inspection of the barn.

In this case Goldman incurs what Tversky and Kahneman call a bias, a cognitive illusion (the base rates neglect) (Vid. Tversky, 1982); by not considering in his argument the base frequency throughout the relevant universe of what Henry knows about barns, to justify Henry's belief or not; but only considering a small part of the same universe, that of the false barns in that area.

What in this instance would have been accidental as a fact, regarding his universe of prior knowledge, is that the barn that Henry saw would have been a false facade; that his belief in that specific barn would not have coincided with reality and, therefore, he was wrong.

In short, Goldman can only implicitly assume (with the finality of assert that there is a justified belief) that Henry makes an induction, and emits his judgment taking for the base rate of it to his universe A of prior knowledge. But next, subreptitiously, he changes the base frequency to a universe B, a proper subset of A, much more limited; and on this change, which is not logically valid, substantiates its argument to deny a posteriori that there is knowledge.

Goldman takes the step from "There is one and only one universe A" to the syntactical generalization "There is some universe X" and from there to the substitute specification "There is a universe B", when he confuses the necessary and sufficient conditions for the justified belief (those of the universe A of Henry's previous knowledge of barns), with those necessary but not sufficient (the consideration only of false barns in that area B).

8. Conclusions.

Linda Zagzebski establishes a procedure for constructing Gettier cases, which, she believes, makes them inescapable:

Start with a case of justified (or warranted) false belief. Make the element of justification (warrant) strong enough for knowledge, but make the belief false ... due to some element of luck. Now emend the case by adding another element of luck, only this time an element which makes the belief true after all. The second element must be independent of the element of warrant so that the degree of warrant is unchanged (Zagzebski 1994, p. 69).

However, there is also a deeper, fallacious structure of the procedure, the oracular, whose recognition allows to escape the Gettier problems. And it is the passage from "There is one and only one" to the simple "There is", and from here, without justification, to the inconsistent change of constant, treating a sentence of belief as if it were a simple sentence; and confusing the necessary and sufficient conditions with those necessary but not sufficient.

That is:

1. Start with an expression (1) referring to an object, a fact, a place or a universe of discourse determined, containing a logical constant c concerning to any of those aspects, with their particular necessary and sufficient conditions for the justified belief.
2. Generalize the same expression towards a new expression (2), using a logical variable x as a replacement for the constant, suppressing some of those necessary conditions.
3. Reinterpret, without logical justification, the general expression (2), with a new logical constant d replacing the variable x , distinct and contradictory of c , referring to an object, a fact, a place, or a specific universe which is in accordance a posteriori with the situation occurring, but that does not meet some suppressed necessary condition. Generating so a new interpreted expression (3), but confusing (3) with (2).

That makes Gettier-like reasoning a sibylline-type argument, logically inconsistent.

References.

- (1) Ayer, A. J., 1956, *The Problem of Knowledge* (London: Macmillan).
- (2) Boh, Ivan, 1985, "Belief, Justification and Knowledge: Some Late Medieval Epistemic Concerns", in *Journal of the Rocky Mountain Medieval and Renaissance Association*, 6: 87–103. Quoted in Ichikawa 2018.
- (3) Chisholm, Roderick, 1957, *Perceiving: A Philosophical Study* (New York: Cornell University Press).
- (4) ——— 1977, *Theory of Knowledge*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- (5) Dretske, Fred, May 1971, "Conclusive reasons", in *Australasian Journal of Philosophy*, 49 (1), 1–22.
doi:10.1080/00048407112341001.
- (6) Dreyfus, George B.J, 1997, *Recognizing Reality: Dharmakirti's Philosophy and its Tibetan Interpretations* (Albany, New York: Suny Press). Quoted in Ichikawa 2018.
- (7) Gettier, Edmund L. 1 June 1963. "Is Justified True Belief Knowledge?", *Analysis*, 23 (6): 121–123. doi:10.1093/analys/23.6.121.
- (8) Goldman, Alvin I., 1976, "Discrimination and Perceptual Knowledge", in *The Journal of Philosophy*, 73(20), pp. 771–791. doi:10.2307/2025679.
- (9) Herodotus, 1975, *Histories*, Books I-II (Cambridge: Harvard University Press and William Heinemann Ltd., Loeb Classical Library).
- (10) Ichikawa, Jonathan, Jenkins y Matthias Steup, Summer 2018, "The Analysis of Knowledge", in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Edward N. Zalta (ed.).
URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/achives/sum2018/entries/knowledge-analysis/>>.
- (11) Lycan, William. G., 2006, "On the Gettier Problem problem", in *Epistemology Futures*, S. Hetherington (ed.) (Oxford: Oxford University Press), pp. 148-168.
- (12) Nozick, Robert, 1981, *Philosophical Explanations* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press).
- (13) Plato, 2005, *Meno and other dialogues*, (New York: Oxford University Press).

(14) Plato, 2015, *Theaetetus and Sophist* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press).

(15) Russell Bertrand, Oct. 1905, On denoting. *Mind*, New Series, Vol. 14, No. 56, pp. 479-493. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mind/XIV.4.479>.

(16) Tversky, Amos y Daniel Kahneman, 1982, "Evidential impact of base rates", in Tversky, Kahneman, and P. Slovic ed., *Judgment under uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases* (New York: Cambridge University Press).

(17) Zagzebski, Linda, 1994, "The Inescapability of Gettier Problems", in *The Philosophical Quarterly*, 44 (174): 65-73, Blackwell Publishing. doi:10.2307/2220147.